

Style for IRRN Contributors

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).

- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).

- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.

- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.

- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.

- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.

- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.

- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.

- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

- Type all contributions double-spaced. ¶

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

An attempt to improve local rice varieties through hybridization

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In an attempt to improve yield, disease resistance, and quality, the local varieties Nizershail and Tepi Boro were crossed with some IRRI strains. The segregating

generations were handled by a combination of pedigree and mass-selection breeding methods. Selection criteria were plant type and yielding ability. Seven F₆ lines are promising with respect to biochemical properties, disease reaction, plant type, and yield: AU16-1, AU21-6, AU16-19-20, AU16-21, AU41-15-18, AU19-3, and AU54-52 (see table). Two F₅ lines, 70.11 and 70.58, also look promising. ¶

Performance of new lines with respect to yield, biochemical constituents, and disease reaction, compared with that of their local parents. Bangladesh Agricultural University.

Line or variety ^a	Parents	Season to which the line was adapted	Yield (t/ha)	Biochemical constituents (%)		Disease reaction ^b		
				Protein	Amylose	Bacterial leaf streak	Bacterial leaf blight	Stem rot
AU21-6	Nizershail/IR532E-420	Aus	5.07	11.8	31	R	MR	R
AU16-1	Nizershail/IR578-175-2-2	Aus	5.35	9.5	28	R	R	MR
AU16-19-20	"	Aman	5.02	6.5	29	-	-	-
AU16-21	"	Aman	5.62	7.8	30	-	-	-
AU41-15-18	Nizershail/IR6-43-48	Aman	4.83	9.1	31	MR	-	-
AU19-3	Nizershail/IR532E-420	Aman	4.81	9.8	27	-	-	-
AU54-52	"	Aman	4.95	9.6	25	MR	-	-
AU70-11	Tepi Boro/IR140-136	Boro	4.95	-	30	MR	MR	R
AU70-58	"	Boro	5.26	-	30	MR	R	R
Nizershail	-	Aman	4.12	7.5	29	-	R	R
Tepi Boro	-	Boro	3.54	10.4	24	MR	R	MR

^aAU = Agricultural University. ^bR = moderately resistant; R = resistant.

IRRI's genetic resources program

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Since 1971 IRRI has collaborated with 12 national agricultural research centers in the field collection of indigenous rice germ plasm. Other workers who have cooperated in the canvassing of rice gene pools in remote areas include university faculty, missionary groups, international

service corps, extension workers, and botanists of other crops. The primary objectives of field collection are to save unimproved varieties that are endangered by the spread of modern varieties and to assemble the minor rices that have not yet been collected.

Since 1972 more than 18,000 seed samples have been collected from South and Southeast Asia; IRRI's staff helped collect more than 7,500 of them. About 4,850 of the samples are reputed to have one or more special characters, such as